

Disease brief_Lyme Borreliosis

	Characteristics	Description
1	Disease and Pathogen	<p>Lyme borreliosis (LB) is a bacterial, tick-borne disease of people and animals (dogs, horses) caused by <i>Borrelia spp.</i> (Gram-negative spirochaetes) of the Lyme Borreliosis group (<i>B. burgdorferi</i>) (2). In humans, typical symptoms of acute infection include fever, headache, fatigue and a characteristic skin rash (erythema migrans). If left untreated, infection can spread to joints, the heart and the nervous system. In animals, clinical signs are nonspecific and reflect the consequences of the immune reaction to the bacteria. Clinical disease in animals is rarely observed.</p> <p>Other <i>Borrelia spp.</i> cause Tickborne Relapsing Fever (TBRF) in humans and animals.</p>
2	Regulatory status in the EU	<p>Borreliosis is a non-WOAH-listed disease in wildlife reported by Members to the WOAH through the voluntary annual report (3).</p> <p>It is a notifiable disease in humans across EU MS (4).</p> <p>Lyme borreliosis is included in Dir 2003/99/EC (in Annex I -point B – “List of zoonoses and zoonotic agents to be monitored according to the epidemiological situation”).</p>
3	Geographical distribution (of autochthonous cases)	<p>Lyme disease is endemic to temperate areas in the northern hemisphere and is seen regularly in Europe, USA and Asia. (5) <i>I. ricinus</i> - current known distribution map <i>I. persulcatus</i> - current known distribution map.</p>
4	Reservoir / main host	<p>Wild rodents and birds are the main reservoir hosts for the bacteria, and transplacental transmission has been documented in rodents in Canada (8). Other reservoir hosts in Europe are: European hedgehogs (<i>Erinaceus europaeus</i>), lacertid lizards, while the role of canids is under investigation (dog, Red fox) (2).</p>
5	Host range / susceptible species (domestic / wild)	<p>Many mammal and bird species. (2) Except for the reservoir hosts, mammals including humans are incidental and dead-end hosts. (6).</p>

6	Vector-borne transmission	Tick vectors of <i>B. burgdorferi s.l.</i> in Europe and Asia, are hard ticks <i>Ixodes ricinus</i> and <i>I. persulcatus</i> . The larvae, nymphs and adult ticks feed on the reservoir host and acquire the pathogen. The transmission to a host occurs at the next life stage. Transovarial transmission is likely (9). Infected ticks transmit the bacteria via saliva during blood feeding (2).
7	Environmental transmission	No.
8	(Main) transmission routes to domestic animals	Tick bite.
9	(Main) transmission routes to humans	Tick bite - There is no evidence that the bacteria can be spread directly from animals to humans. (2)
10	Disease indicators	In dogs: lameness; in horses: neuroborreliosis; in cattle: decreased milk production; (1) Clinical borreliosis is unlikely to be observed in wild mammals and birds.
11	a) Clinical signs	Most animals do not develop clinical illness after infection. Infections of animals are often overlooked, or symptoms are not attributed to Borreliosis. This is even more relevant for wildlife which is by nature not well observed (1). Cows may experience decreased milk production. (2) In dogs, clinical signs are intermittent, shifting lameness, fever, anorexia, lethargy and lymphadenopathy with or without swollen, painful joints. Horses' clinical signs include uveitis, cutaneous lymphoma, atrophy of spinal muscles, dysphagia, laryngeal dysfunction, facial paresis, spinal cord ataxia, paresis, behavioural changes, and hyperesthesia. Borrelia infection in hedgehogs causes erythema migrans rash, anorexia, ataxia, stiff gait, joint effusion and death. Red foxes infected with <i>B. afzelii</i> experience inflammation of the eye, kidney and liver. (1)
		Culture and PCR do not reliably detect spirochetes. Blood samples are generally negative, because the organism resides in tissue and not in the circulation. (1).
12	b) Seroconversion	Animals may be seropositive without clinical signs. (2)
13	c) Other disease indicators	Musculoskeletal problems. (2)

14	Indicators relevant for monitoring (Indicator-based surveillance)	Decreased milk production, neurological signs, incoordination accompanied by arthritis and lameness. (1)
15	Test systems available for infection/disease detection	Identification of the agent: Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) on ticks Serological tests: Indirect fluorescent antibody (IFA) test; Antibody capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA); as well as: <i>B. burgdorferi</i> serotyping using monoclonal antibodies (MA) against OspA and OspC bacterial surface proteins and C6 peptide-based assay to identify antibodies in dogs. (2)
16	Surveillance component options (+ rationale)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Serological surveillance of dogs in high-risk regions; Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk regions where the vector is endemic (ticks dragging or flagging); Pathogen detection in ticks from wild rodents in high-risk regions; <p>All the systems described are to be considered complementary to human LB surveillance already in place in some MSs.</p>

		GENERAL POPULATION	EXPOSED	INFECTED	INFECTIOUS	SYMPTOMATIC	GP/VD VISIT	DEAD	Component name
VECTOR-borne diseases									
LYME BORRELIOSIS	Dogs								Serological surveillance of dogs in high-risk areas
	Wild birds								No surveillance component specifically designed
	Rodents								No surveillance component specifically designed
	Ixodes ricinus								Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk areas where the vector is endemic
	Human								Pathogen detection in ticks collected from rodents in high-risk areas
									Surveillance components targetting human were not in scope

17	Comparison of surveillance component options (main advantages/disadvantages)	<p>1. <u>Serological surveillance of dogs in high-risk regions</u> – ADVANTAGES: The target population is known in most EU MS. Specific samples or samples submitted to reference centres and laboratories can be used. This could be combined with awareness campaigns to veterinarians. DISADVANTAGES: Only historical exposure can be measured, and no prevalence can be derived.</p> <p>2. <u>Pathogen detection in ticks in high-risk regions where the vector is endemic (ticks dragging or flagging)</u> - ADVANTAGES: system already in place in some EU countries; Can be utilised to study multiple diseases transmitted by the same vector. DISADVANTAGES: Expensive, labour intensive.</p> <p><u>Pathogen detection in ticks from wild rodents in high-risk regions</u> – ADVANTAGES: Detection of Borrelia in rodents is challenging, while it is easier in ticks. Feeding ticks are likely to get infected with Borrelia. However, probability of Borreliosis transmission depends on the species composition of the local rodent population; not all tick hosts are good reservoir hosts for Borrelia. Better knowledge can inform ecosystem management to reduce transmission probability [7]. Specifically designed samples or other samples that reach reference centres or National Wildlife Research Centres can be used. There is no established surveillance for diseases in rodents at EU level. DISADVANTAGES: Ticks from the same host are correlated. Representativeness must target host individuals and thus expertise (trapping) is needed to collect a representative sample of the rodent population. NB: pest control is not a useful sampling source.</p>
18	Countries which already carry out surveillance for this pathogen	No MS conducts systematic surveillance for LB in animals in Europe; investigations are conducted for research purposes.
19	References	<p>1) MSD Veterinary Manual, Lyme Borreliosis in Animals (Lyme Disease) By Nadine A. Vogt, BSc (Hons), DVM, MSc, University of Guelph, Medically Reviewed Mar 2021 Modified Oct 2022</p> <p>2) WOAHA Technical disease card - Borrelia spp. (Infection with) Aetiology Epidemiology Diagnosis Prevention and Control Potential Impacts of Disease Agent Beyond Clinical Illness References, 2020</p>

		<p>3) WOAHA data on Borreliosis, 2022</p> <p>4) Garcia-Vozmediano A, De Meneghi D, Sprong H, Portillo A, Oteo JA, Tomassone L. A One Health Evaluation of the Surveillance Systems on Tick-Borne Diseases in the Netherlands, Spain and Italy. <i>Vet Sci</i>. 2022 Sep 14;9(9):504. doi: 10.3390/vetsci9090504. PMID: 36136720; PMCID: PMC9501221.</p> <p>5) ECDC Factsheet about Borreliosis, 6 Mar 2016</p> <p>6) Van den Wijngaard Cees C, Hofhuis Agnetha, Simões Mariana, Rood Entje, van Pelt Wilfrid, Zeller Herve, Van Bortel Wim. Surveillance perspective on Lyme borreliosis across the European Union and European Economic Area. <i>Euro Surveill</i>. 2017;22(27):pii=30569.</p> <p>7) The evolving story of <i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i> sensu lato transmission in Europe https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-022-07445-3</p> <p>8) Zinck, C. B., & Lloyd, V. K. (2022). <i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i> and <i>Borrelia miyamotoi</i> in Atlantic Canadian wildlife. <i>Plos one</i>, 17(1), e0262229.</p> <p>9) Hauck, D., Jordan, D., Springer, A. et al. Transovarial transmission of <i>Borrelia</i> spp., <i>Rickettsia</i> spp. and <i>Anaplasma phagocytophilum</i> in <i>Ixodes ricinus</i> under field conditions extrapolated from DNA detection in questing larvae, 2020. <i>Parasites Vectors</i>, 13, 176. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04049-7</p>
20	Additional comments	<p>The overall mean prevalence of <i>B. burgdorferi</i> genospecies in ticks in Europe has been estimated at about 12% with higher prevalence in adult ticks than in nymphs. (5)</p>